

Fast and selective removal of bismuth(III) ions by titaniumcerium tungstate : Sorption kinetics and thermodynamics

M. A. Dhanitha and C. Janardanan*

Post Graduate and Research Department of Chemistry, Sree Narayana College, Kannur-670 007, Kerala, India

E-mail : dhanithabiju@gmail.com, jeeje_dianthus@yahoo.com

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Abstract : An advanced inorganic cation exchange material titaniumcerium tungstate (TCW) has been synthesized and characterized by various analytical techniques. The material showed higher selectivity towards bismuth metal ion and its sorption kinetics was studied. The sorption data were subjected to Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms for the mathematical description of the adsorption equilibrium and the data fixed well with Langmuir isotherm model. The rate of adsorption of bismuth(III) on TCW was studied by using the first order rate equation proposed by Lagergren and the equilibrium data fixed very well with this equation. The adsorption was feasible, spontaneous and exothermic, which was confirmed by the evaluation of thermodynamic parameters viz. ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 . Analytical utility of the material was explored by separating bismuth(III) metal ions from synthetic mixtures.

Keywords : Bismuth, adsorption isotherm, kinetics of adsorption, thermodynamic parameters.

Introduction

Environmental pollution and its harmful effect on habitat have been studied intensively during last decades¹. Unplanned industrialization, urbanization, pollution explosion, change in life-style, over exploitation of natural resources, commercial establishment and modern agricultural practices have degraded the quality of environment. The main effects being faced are; Continental invasion of air and water, Marine pollution through waste discharges, Release of variety of chemical and biological contaminants into the water bodies, on land and in air, Ground water pollution, Acid rains and nuclear fallout. These effects are not only covering the pollution of environment but also are responsible in creating genetic erosion in plants, animals including human beings and microorganisms. Water is a prime natural resource and is a basic human need. The availability of adequate water supply in terms of its quality and quantity is essential for the existence of life².

Among the toxic heavy metal ions, which present potential health hazard to aquatic animals and human are Pb, Cd, Cr, V, Bi and Mn. The maximum tolerance limit for bismuth(III) for public water supply is 0.5 mg/L. Toxicity of metal depends on the type of metal, dose and the

ionic form. Toxicity of bismuth(III) and its salt include malaise, kidney damage, albuminuria, diarrhea and skin reactions, tremor of the finger and hands, nephropathy, osteoarthropathy, hepatitis, and neuropathology³. Therefore the removal of bismuth is essential for the elimination of bismuth contamination.

Literature survey reveals that there are many methods namely coagulation, precipitation, ion exchange and adsorption, for removal of bismuth(III) metal ions from aqueous medium. However, adsorption is an easy and economical process for removal and retrieval of cation from aqueous medium, efficiency of adsorption process mainly depends on nature of adsorbent, adsorbate, pH, concentration, temperature, time of agitation etc.⁴. The cheap and efficient adsorbents can cater the need of population in the rural areas and the population in the industrial area where safe drinking water is not available.

In the present work, an advanced inorganic material titaniumcerium tungstate (TCW) has been synthesized well characterized. The aim of the present study was to investigate the bismuth adsorption characteristics of the exchanger taking into account equilibrium, kinetic and thermodynamic aspects. The Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm were applied to describe and predict the adsorption

equilibrium. Legergren's first order rate equation was applied to study the kinetics of adsorption. The results of the studies were utilized to evaluate thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 .

Experimental

Synthesis of ion exchange material :

Different samples were precipitated by adding a mixture of 0.05 M titanium chloride and 0.05 M ammonium ceric nitrate solution to 0.05 M solution of sodium tungstate with continuous stirring in different volume ratios (Table 1). The desired pH was adjusted by adding dilute HNO₃. The precipitates were kept in the mother liquors for 24 h at room temperature. The precipitates of different samples were filtered. After filtration continuous washing of all the samples was done to remove excess acid, with distilled water. pH of the effluents was checked with the help of pH paper. When the effluent becomes neutral, precipitates were assumed to be free from excess acid. Now these samples were kept in an oven at 40 ± 1 °C for drying. The dried granules were converted into the H⁺ form by keeping them immersed with HNO₃ (1.0 M) for 24 h with occasional shaking and intermittently replacing the supernatant liquid with fresh acid. The material thus obtained was then washed with demineralised water to remove the excess acid before drying finally at 40 ± 1 °C and sieved to obtain particles of size 60–100 mesh⁵.

Table 1. Conditions of synthesis and properties of different samples of titaniumcerium tungstate

Sample	Molar conc. (M)			Mixing volume ratio	pH	Appearance	I.E.C. (meq/g)
	Ti	Ce	W				
TCW1	0.05	0.05	0.05	1 : 1 : 1	1		1.06
TCW2	0.05	0.05	0.05	1 : 2 : 3	1	Yellow	0.89
TCW3	0.05	0.05	0.05	1 : 2 : 4	1	glassy	1.42
TCW4	0.05	0.05	0.05	2 : 1 : 3	1	solids	1.04
TCW5	0.05	0.05	0.05	2 : 1 : 4	1		0.79

Instrumentation :

TCW has been analyzed for titanium, cerium and tungsten by EDS method. Thermal analysis was performed on a Shimadzu DT-30 thermal analyzer at a heating rate of 10 K per minute. FTIR spectra was obtained using

KBr wafer on a Perkin-Elmer paragon 1000 spectrophotometer. X-Ray diffractograms were obtained on an X-ray diffractometer Bruker AXS D8 using Cu-K α radiation with a nickel filter. Jeol Model JSM-6390LV for Scanning Electron Microscopic analysis and Jeol Model Jed-2300 for Energy Dispersive Spectrometric measurements were used for various physiochemical characterizations. For kinetic studies, a shaker with a temperature variation of 5 °C was used. UV-Visible spectrophotometer model JASCO V660 was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

Sorption studies :

The adsorption experiments were carried out by agitating 200 mg of adsorbent with 20 mL of bismuth(III) solution (0.01 M) at 150 rpm on a shaker at 298 K. The concentration of bismuth(III) remained in the solution, after being centrifuged was analysed spectrophotometrically with xylenol orange as chromogenic reagent ($\lambda_{\max} = 545$ nm)⁶. In this study, the effects of several factors such as, pH, concentration of bismuth(III) solution (0.005–0.05 M), adsorbent doses (0.005–0.05 g), temperature (303, 313 and 323 K) and contact time on bismuth(III) removal efficiency were examined.

Adsorption isotherm studies :

For adsorption isotherm studies, 10 mL metal ion solution of different concentrations with increment of 0.005 M (0.01 M to 0.05 M) was equilibrated for a specific period of time with 100 mg of exchanger in stoppered conical flasks at desired temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K). The supernatant liquid was removed immediately and the metal concentration evaluated spectrophotometrically⁶.

Kinetic and thermodynamic studies :

TCW particles of definite mesh size [30–60 mesh (ASTM)] were used to evaluate various kinetic and thermodynamic parameters. pH of the solution was adjusted to the value at which maximum sorption of respective metal ion takes place. Metal ion solution (10 ml of 0.01 M), was shaken with 100 mg of exchanger in stoppered conical flasks at the desired temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K) and at different time intervals with increments of 10 min (10, 20, 30, ... 180). The supernatant liquid was removed immediately after each prescribed time interval and the metal concentration evaluated spectrophotometri-

cally with xylenol orange as chromogenic reagent ($\lambda_{\max} = 545 \text{ nm}$). Results obtained from this study were utilized to evaluate kinetic and thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0) using the equations which are given in the Results and discussion section.

Results and discussion

Characterization :

TCW synthesized is obtained as yellow glassy solids. EDS analysis shows the ratio of Ti : Ce : W to be 1 : 1.1 : 2.4. The Na^+ ion exchange capacity of selected sample at room temperature is 1.42 meq g^{-1} .

The FTIR spectrum (Fig. 1(a)) of TCW exhibits a broad band in the region 3556 cm^{-1} , which is attributed to asymmetric and symmetric hydroxyl -OH stretches. A sharp medium band at 1631 cm^{-1} is attributed to aqua (H-O-H) bending. A band in the region 2370 cm^{-1} showed the presence of Ti-O bond⁷. The band at 2941 cm^{-1} indicates deformation vibrations of the coordinated water molecules and the band in the region of 1514 cm^{-1} repre-

sents deformation vibrations of metal hydroxyl groups and interstitial water molecules. The bands at 1116 cm^{-1} , 960 cm^{-1} and 673 cm^{-1} express the presence of metal-oxygen stretching vibrations⁸. TGA of TCW (Fig. 1(b)) shows a sharp change within the temperature up to $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to the loss of external water molecules, after which a gradual weight loss is observed till $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This may be due to the condensation of structural hydroxyl groups. The scanning electron microscope image (Fig. 1(c)) of titaniumcerium tungstate explains the particles were broad in size range, having an irregular shape and no sign of crystalline structure. X-Ray diffractogram (Fig. 1(d)) of the material also supports its amorphous nature.

Sorption studies :

Effect of adsorbent dose and concentration of metal ion :

Fig. 2(a) shows the percentage adsorption of bismuth solution on TCW exchanger versus adsorbent dosage. It is evident from the figure that the percentage adsorption

Fig. 1. (a) FTIR, (b) TGA, (c) SEM and (d) XRD of TCW.

of bismuth increases with increasing adsorbent dose, which is due to the availability of more adsorption sites at higher concentrations of the adsorbent⁹. Maximum of 92.5% bismuth is adsorbed by about 0.5 g of the adsorbent. The response of adsorbate dose on the removal of bismuth(III) is presented in Fig. 2(b). The observations reveal that with an increase in the adsorbate dose, the adsorption efficiency of the exchanger decreases. This is due to increase in metal concentration, the surface area and saturated active sites of the adsorbent and hence the adsorption efficiency is decreased.

Effect of pH on the removal of bismuth(III) :

The effect of pH on the removal of bismuth(III) is shown in Fig. 3. Experiments were conducted at the con-

Fig. 2. (a) Effect of adsorbent dose and (b) effect of Bi concentration.

stant initial bismuth(III) concentration, adsorbent dose of 100 mg/20 mL and the contact time of 4 h. The pH of the aqueous solution is an important controlling parameter in the adsorption process. It was observed that the percentage removal of bismuth(III) is higher when the pH is about 2 and then, it decreases with increase of pH.

Effect of contact time and temperature on the sorption

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on the removal of bismuth(III).

Effect of contact time, reaction temperature and % uptake of metal ion is presented in Table 2. It is observed that sorption increases gradually with increase in contact time and reaches a maximum value after which randomness is observed. Increase in % uptake could be attrib-

Table 2. Effect of contact time and temperature on the sorption of bismuth(III) towards TCW

Time (min)	Percentage uptake of Bi ^{III}		
	303 K	313 K	323 K
10	13.2	27.6	40.2
20	36.4	48.9	59.1
30	47.6	65.8	83.3
40	62.1	84.2	88.7
50	79.3	89.4	90.2
60	80.9	92.1	92.7
70	84.6		
80	87.7		
90	89.4		
100	91.5		
120			
140			

uted to two different sorption processes, namely, a fast ion exchange followed by chemisorption¹⁰. Initially the rate of adsorption was very fast, in 20 min the adsorption was 36.4% and in 60 min adsorption increases up to 80.9%. Then after 100 min the adsorption of bismuth(III) was found to be 91.5% which remains constant thereafter. This may be due to availability of the all active sites of adsorbent at the initial stage so rapid adsorption was observed and as the time increased the repulsive forces increased due to adsorbed adsorbate. It is also observed that the uptake of bismuth(III) increases with increase in temperature, which indicates the uptake to be an ion exchange mechanism. Percentage uptake has been calculated using formula, $[(C_0 - C_e)/C_0] \times 100$, where C_0 is the initial concentration of metal ion in mg/L and C_e , the final concentration of metal ion in mg/L. The time taken for attainment of equilibrium is bismuth(III) 100 min.

Adsorption isotherms :

Langmuir isotherm theory¹¹ is based on the assumption that adsorption on a homogeneous surface and is used to determine the maximum capacity of adsorbent.

The linearised form of the Langmuir adsorption isotherm equation is,

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{K_L q_m} + \frac{C_e}{q_m} \quad (1)$$

where K_L is the Langmuir constant; q_m is the maximum adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1}) and q_e is the adsorbed amount of bismuth(III) at equilibrium (mg g^{-1}). The values of K_L and q_m were determined from experimental data by linear regression, i.e. a plot of C_e/q_e versus C_e (Fig. 4(a)) indicates a straight line of slope $1/q_m$ and intercept of $1/(K_L q_m)$.

Freundlich isotherm is a model based on the distribution of solute between the solid phase and liquid phase at equilibrium. The Freundlich equation is expressed as follows;

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n}$$

where K_F and n are Freundlich constants related to the adsorption capacity, adsorption intensity respectively. The values of K_F and n were obtained from the linear plots of $\ln q_e$ versus $\ln C_e$ (Fig. 4(b)).

The data in Table 3 presents the results, along with

Fig. 4. (a) Langmuir isotherm and (b) Freundlich isotherm.

associated correlation coefficients (R^2). Also the data in Table 3 reveals that according to the correlation coefficients, the Langmuir model yields a better fit than the Freundlich model. Maximum monolayer adsorption of bismuth on the TCW showed that the exchanger used in the present study has a relatively good adsorption capacity. Strong positive evidence for the good adsorption capacity is also obtained from the correlation coefficients

Table 3. Parameters for Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms

T (K)	Langmuir			Freundlich		
	q_m (mg/g)	K_L (L/mol)	R^2	K_f	n	R^2
303	1.1601	131.68	0.9996	0.0154	2.2050	0.8257
313	0.9961	159.63	0.9996	0.0363	2.0963	0.8621
323	1.0590	185.04	0.9999	0.0466	2.0898	0.8129

R^2 as shown in Table 3.

Kinetics of adsorption :

2 g of the exchanger, TCW and 200 mL 0.01 M bismuth(III) solution were taken in 1000 mL R.B. and shaken vigorously for about 4 h. After every 10 min, 5 mL sample of the solution was withdrawn for the first two hours and subsequently, the interval between the samples withdrawn was increased to 15 min. The concentration of the metal ions in the sample withdrawn were determined spectrophotometrically and were designated as C_t and the value of the concentration of the metal ion on the exchanger at the same time interval was estimated using the relation.

$$q = \frac{(C_0 - C_t)}{M} V$$

The rate of adsorption of bismuth(III) on titaniumcerium tungstate was studied by using the first order rate equation proposed by Lagergren.

$$K_{ad} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \left(\frac{C_0}{C_t} \right)$$

where K_{ad} is the rate constant for adsorption. The plot of $\log C_t$ vs t is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Lagergren plot system for TCW-bismuth(III).

The linear plot of $\log C_t$ vs time (t) for the adsorption shows the validity of Lagergren equation and suggest the first order kinetics.

Thermodynamics of adsorption :

Spontaneity of a process can be determined by thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy change (ΔH^0), free energy change (ΔG^0) and entropy change (ΔS^0). A spontaneous process will show a decrease in ΔG^0 value with increasing temperature. The thermodynamic parameters of adsorption, i.e. enthalpy change (ΔH^0), free energy change (ΔG^0) and entropy change (ΔS^0) were calculated using the following equations¹² :

$$\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K_L$$

$$\ln K_L = \Delta S^0/R - \Delta H^0/RT$$

where R is the general gas constant ($\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), $K_L = K_{ads}/K_d$ is the Langmuir adsorption constant and T is the temperature (K). ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values can be obtained from the slope and intercept of the Van't Hoff plots of $\ln K_L$ (from the Langmuir isotherm) versus $1/T$ ¹³. The results of these thermodynamic calculations are shown in Fig. 6 and Table 4.

Fig. 6. Plot of the Langmuir adsorption constant ($\ln K_L$) vs temperature ($1/T$).

Table 4. Thermodynamic constants for the adsorption of bismuth(III) on TCW

T (K)	$\ln K_L$	ΔG^0 (kJ/mol)	ΔH^0 (kJ/mol)	ΔS^0 (kJ/mol/K)
303	4.88	-12.29		
313	5.07	-13.19	-14.54	0.0035
323	5.22	-14.02		

The negative values of ΔG^0 (Table 4) reflect the feasibility of the process and the values become more negative with increase in temperature as well as it shows that, the adsorption is highly favorable and spontaneous. Negative value of ΔH^0 indicates that the adsorption process is exothermic. The positive values of ΔS^0 show the increased disorder and randomness at the solid solution interface of bismuth ion with TCW. The enhancement of adsorption capacity of the exchanger at higher temperatures was attributed to the enlargement of pore size and activation of the adsorbent surface. The enrichment in the adsorption capacity may be due to the chemical interaction between the adsorbate and the adsorbent, creation of some new adsorption sites on the adsorbent at higher temperatures¹⁴.

Analysis of synthetic mixtures :

In order to extend the utility of the material, it was used for the determination of bismuth(III) content in synthetic mixtures of associated metal ions. A similar procedure was applied to determine the bismuth(III) content in synthetic mixtures of Pb^{II}, Bi^{III}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II} and Ni^{II}. The results are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. Selective separation of bismuth(III) from synthetic mixtures containing Bi³⁺, Zn²⁺ [2.15 mg], Mg²⁺ [2.97 mg] and Ni²⁺ [1.93 mg]

Amount of metal ion loaded (mg)	Amount of metal ion found (mg)	Recovery (%)	Eluent used	Volume of eluent (ml)
5.22	4.86	93.10	0.5 M HNO ₃	70
4.96	4.79	96.57	0.5 M HNO ₃	50

The results showed that it is a promising and useful material where an effective method is needed for the removal and isolation of bismuth(III) ions from industrial effluents and other bismuth contaminated solutions.

Conclusion

The adsorbent was easily prepared and was found to be economically affordable, which showed the maximum percentage removal of bismuth(III) (91.5%) even at room temperature. The isotherm models such as Langmuir and Freundlich were studied, amongst them Langmuir equation showed the more applicability to the experimental data than Freundlich isotherm. The rate of adsorption

was studied using Lagergren first order kinetic equation and it was found that the data fits better with this model. The adsorption was feasible, spontaneous and exothermic, which was confirmed by the evaluation of thermodynamic parameters viz. ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 . The material was effective for the successful separation of bismuth(III) from synthetic waste water, shows the applicability of the material towards the removal of bismuth metal ion from industrial waste water.

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